

Evaluation of relationship between systemic osteoporosis and reduction of residual ridge in edentulous patients

Simran Marwah

Corresponding author

Dept of prosthodontics and implantology

Ranjeet Deshmukh Dental college and research centre, Nagpur 440019

Author Details

Simran Marwah

Under graduate student

Dept of Prosthodontics, RDDC &RC, Nagpur

Dr Saeesh Deshpande: corresponding author

Assoc Professor

Dept of prosthodontics, RDDC &RC, Nagpur

INTRODUCTION:

Residual ridge is a term used to describe the shape of the alveolar ridge that remains following a tooth extraction. It is a term used to describe that portion of residual bone along with the soft tissue structures supporting it that remain after extractions [1]. However, after extraction of teeth the alveolar portion of the jaws atrophies and leads to the formation of residual ridge. [2]. The success of any removal complete denture prosthesis depends on factors like retention, stability, support, architecture of jaw for which a good ridge is imperative. But after extractions not only the quantity but also the quality of the residual ridge decreases. [3]

Following a tooth extraction, the socket is temporarily closed by a cascade reaction involving inflammatory reactions. This wound healing cascade is a complex milieu of cytokines, inflammatory cells and growth factors. New epithelial tissue is formed by proliferation and migration of cells within first week of healing. Within a span of six months the socket is filled with newly formed bone. After healing of wound the residual ridge undergoes catabolic remodeling which is a slow- life long process. [4][5]

Atwood et al implied that residual ridge resorption is process that depends on multiple factors and described them as anatomic, metabolic, functional and prosthetic. The metabolic factors focused on age, sex, general health and cellular activity of osteoblast and osteoclast. [6]

Osteoporosis is a systemic disease which shows a decrease in skeletal mass without alteration in the chemical composition of bone. It has been linked to a variety of risk factor such as age, sex, diet, and smoking, some systemic conditions as well as dietary Calcium intake. Osteoporosis accelerates bone resorption in maxilla and mandible.

In osteopenia bone is more radiolucent, has a thinner cortex and trabecular width is altered and can be compared to a coarse net like structure. **Jergas et al** said diagnosis of osteoporosis on basis of osteopenic appearance of bone is uncertain method but clinically an important one. [7]

The drawbacks of residual ridge resorption include loss of sulcus depth and width, loss of denture stability and retention especially in the mandible, sunken appearance of cheeks, altered inter arch relationship, unsatisfactory facial aesthetics and an altered vertical dimension of occlusion. [1]

Various methods have been used to measure the ridge resorption like clinical roentgenographic studies, serial cephalometric roentgenogram [8]. And most widely used is Wical and Swoope method as they stated that the relationship of the mental foramen with inferior border of mandible remained relatively constant and wasn't affected by bone resorption above the mental foramen. [9]

Hence, to determine the co-relation of residual ridge resorption with age, sex, and most importantly bone mineral density of an individual is of clinical importance. It will help the doctor in efficient prognosis and treatment planning for success of the removal dental prosthesis for the patient. Hence the following study is carried out

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

Aim- To evaluate the co-relation between Age, Sex, Degree of Osteoporosis and residual ridge resorption in completely edentulous patients.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

- **ETHICAL APPROVAL-** the study protocol was approved by the ethics committee and the study was conducted at the department of prosthodontics ,
- **APPARATUS USED-** digital OPG machine, bone mineral density measuring ultrasound machine, dietary case history for calcium intake.
- **SOURCE OF DATA-** the study was carried out on 30 completely edentulous patients both males and females attending department of prosthodontics in college.

SELECTION CRITERIA:**INCLUSION CRITERIA-**

All patients who were strictly completely edentulous were included in the study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA-

- Patients with neurological deficits
- Patients with metabolic bone disease, cancers with bone metastasis
- Patients with any renal impairment

METHODOLOGY:

A community wide cross-sectional study was carried among completely edentulous patients at our dental college after getting approval from the institutional ethics committee and obtaining consent from the patients after briefing them about the procedure. The ' T-score' of these patients was recorded using an ultrasound machine that measures the bone mineral density. After taking their consent a standard panoramic radiograph was made.

All the OPG's were taken by the same operator for a standard patient positioning.

the specifications of the machine include-

- OPG was made using Carestream (CS 8100SC) Machine
- On standard Kodak C – matt green sensitive 8 inches by 10 inches film
- Exposure parameters include- 72 kV, 12 mA and 10.8 seconds.

Only those OPG's where anatomical landmarks used to assess resorption by Wical and Swoope method that is the mental foramen, inferior border of mental foramen and superior and inferior border of mandible, were clearly visible on at least one side right or left were taken into consideration for analysis.

The amount of resorption was calculated according to Wical and Swoope method [9]

Type of study- in-vivo study

Study population- study was conducted among 30 completely edentulous patients attending our college

Sample size- about 30 completely edentulous patients who were attending the dental college were considered in the study (25 male and 5 female patients)

DENSITOMETRIC TEST-

A bone mineral density test is used to measure bone mineral content and density. Bone mineral density gives us an account of the bone mass which if decreased is suggestive of brittle bones that are more prone to fractures, osteopenia and osteoporosis. Ultrasound measures the speed of sound (SOS) and broadband attenuation (BUA) as they pass the bone. It is safe as no radiation is used, easily accessible, comparatively affordable, portable, less time consuming to the doctor and patient and can be used in easily accessible sites like radius, wrist, fingers, tibia and heel. It helps the healthcare provider to assess and treat the condition before it has advanced too far to be treated. The obtained value is called as the T-score.

According to World Health Organisation osteoporosis can be evaluated on the basis of T-score as [14] -

T - SCORE	WHO CLASSIFICATION
Within 1SD(+1 or -1)	Normal bone density
Between (-1 & -2.5)SD	Osteopenia (low bone density)
More than -2.5 SD	Osteoporosis

WICAL AND SWOOPE ANALYSIS-

As per this method the residual ridge resorption can be calculated by the formula

$$R=3X-Y$$

The anatomical landmarks taken for the calculations are

- Mental foramen
- Lower level of mental foramen
- Superior and inferior border of mandible

Here,

R= amount of mandibular residual ridge resorption

X= distance from inferior border of mandible to lower border of mental foramen

L= height of mandibular residual alveolar ridge

3x= considered as actual ridge height

Wical & Swoope method.

RESULTS:

Table 1:

Sr.no	Gender	Osteopenia	%	Osteoporosis	%	Grand Total	%
1	F	2	0.07	3	0.10	5	0.17
2	M	23	0.77	2	0.07	25	0.83
	Grand Total	25	0.83	5	0.17	30	1.00

The Fisher exact test statistic value is 0.0219. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Table 2.1: Age and WHO classification

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Osteopenia	25	1427	57.08	83.08
Osteoporosis	5	308	61.6	68.80

ANOVA

Table 2.2

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	85.13	1	85.13	1.05	0.31	4.20
Within Groups	2269.04	28	81.04			
Total	2354.17	29				

Table 3.1: Residual ridge resorption (in cm)

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
M	25	18.3	0.73	0.22
F	5	5.8	1.16	0.45

ANOVA

Table 3.2:

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	0.76	1	0.76	3.01	0.09	4.20
Within Groups	7.11	28	0.25			
Total	7.87	29				

Table 4.1: T-score of male and female

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
M	25	13	0.52	143.53
F	5	-11.5	-2.3	0.21

ANOVA

Table 4.2:

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	33.13	1	33.13	0.27	0.61	4.20
Within Groups	3445.64	28	123.06			
Total	3478.78	29				

Table 5.1: residual ridge resorption (in cm)

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
40-50	4	1.4	0.35	0.03
50-60	15	13.7	0.91	0.21
60-70	11	9	0.82	0.39

ANOVA

Table 5.2:

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	1.01	2	0.50	1.98	0.16	3.35
Within Groups	6.86	27	0.25			
Total	7.87	29				

Table 6.1: T- score with different age groups

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
40-50	4	-6.6	-1.65	0.04
50-60	15	30.4	2.03	239.92
60-70	11	-22.3	-2.03	0.22

Table 6.2:

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	117.63	2	58.82	0.47	0.63	3.35
Within Groups	3361.14	27	124.49			
Total	3478.78	29				

Table 7: Correlation

	Age	Residual ridge resorption (in cm)	T-SCORE (bone mineral density score)
Age	1		
Residual ridge resorption (in cm)	0.27	1	
T-SCORE(bone mineral density score)	-0.01	0.23	1

- Correlation:

: Correlation between Age and Residual ridge resorption (in cm) is 0.27

(The P-Value is .149029. The result is *not* significant at $p < .05$.)

: Correlation between Age and T-SCORE(bone mineral density score) is -0.01

The P-Value is .958173. The result is *not* significant at $p < .05$.)

: Correlation between T-SCORE(bone mineral density score) and *Residual ridge resorption (in cm)* is 0.23(The P-Value is .221441. The result is *not* significant at $p < .05$)

DISCUSSION:

- Progressive ridge resorption decreases the denture supporting area. It is a slow lifelong process and a major problem for prosthodontists in fabricating a complete denture prosthesis for edentulous patients. [15]. Patients might not be aware of the poor fit of the denture until the loss of denture bearing area is so great that subjective symptoms occur. [16]
- The results of this study showed that [Table 1] residual ridge resorption showed positive correlation with gender difference after statistical analysis by Fisher exact test with the value of 0.0219. where p value was $< .05$ and is considered to be significant. Osteopenia was recorded among 25 patients and osteoporosis was recorded among 5 patients with variance of 83.08 and 68.80 respectively. [table 2.1]. But there was no significant statistical difference osteopenia and osteoporotic groups when compared on the basis of age. When compared on basis of gender and residual ridge resorption [table 3.1] female showed average bone resorption of 1.16 and males showed 0.73. If we see on the basis of average bone resorption, females showed a higher rate of resorption as compared to men, this is in accordance to studies by Bianchi et al[17], Lopez Roldan et al [18] and Al jabrah et al[19] who also

reported a higher average residual ridge resorption in females than in males. In a study by **Devlin H et al [20]** he said that the increase in residual ridge resorption in females is due to menopause as there is deficiency of estrogen hormone. Estrogen was shown to be an important factor as in a study by **Nishimura I et al [21]** it was shown that estrogen has an apoptotic effect on osteoclasts. However, in this study as per results is not statistically significant, as when compared for ANOVA test the p value came to be 0.09 [table 3.2].

- Increasing age showed direct variation with residual ridge resorption [table 5.1]. These average resorption values when viewed are in relation with studies by **Bianchi et al [17]**, **Bairam et al [22]**, **Imirzalioglu P et al [23]** that showed a direct variation of residual ridge resorption with age. A major reason for this is a reduction in bone mineral density, decrease in physical activity, dietary calcium intake, less oestrogen secretion in women with advancing age and genetics can also lead to age related bone loss. However, there is no statistical significance found as p value came to be 0.16 [table 5.2]. Such results were found to be in studies carried by **Hirai et al [24]**, **Lopez Roldan et al [18]** and **Atwood [6]** and **Narhi et al [25]** who did not find any significant correlation between age and ridge resorption. One of the reasons for this could be the measuring of resorption rate after a short period of extraction of teeth. Studies that were carried out for many years showed a positive correlation between age and bone resorption.

- All these findings suggests that it is important to retain teeth for as long as possible because with increase in number of loss of teeth there is increase in residual ridge resorption [26]. Studies by **Kordatzis k et al** [27] showed that implant supported dentures show less reduction in alveolar bone than conventional dentures.

CONCLUSION:

Within the limitations of the study, given time period for research of 2 months and data obtained it can be concluded that-

- There is a positive correlation with gender difference, osteopenia and osteoporosis when Fisher's exact test was used, and the p value was <0.05
- Even though statistically significant results weren't found due to small sample size and less ratio of female patients than to male in the 2 month study conducted, when average bone resorption values were compared, the females showed a higher residual ridge resorption than males.
- With an increase in age there is increase in residual ridge resorption when we view the average values of the three age groups. However due to small sample size there is no statistical significance as p value was not < 0.05 .
- : There is no statistically significant difference between T-SCORE (bone mineral density score) of male and females
- There is no statistically significant difference between T-SCORE (bone mineral density score) of three defined age groups

Hence the study opens up gates for appropriate treatment planning for a removal dental prosthesis for edentulous patients. As an attempt to preserve the alveolar bone either by retaining teeth for longer span of time, using implants and even implant supported dentures.

SUMMARY:

INTRODUCTION: The success of any removal complete denture prosthesis depends on factors like retention, stability, support, architecture of jaw for which a good ridge is imperative. But after extractions not only the quantity but also the quality of the residual ridge decreases. [3]

OBJECTIVES: To evaluate the co-relation between Age, Sex, Degree of Osteoporosis and residual ridge resorption in completely edentulous patients.

METHODOLOGY: A cross sectional study was undertaken considering 30 completely edentulous patients from the dental college. Bone mineral density score was recorded using ultrasound and an OPG (orthopantomogram) was taken after taking consent from the patients. Using Wical and Swoope method the residual ridge resorption was recorded.

RESULTS: Due to small sample size of patients statistically significant results weren't recorded as p value was not <0.05 but when average values were compared – there was increase in residual ridge resorption with increasing age and females showed higher alveolar bone resorption than males.

CONCLUSION: There is a need to preserve the alveolar bone architecture in edentulous patients. Even though resorption of bone is an inevitable process, combined efforts by a dentist and physician to educate patients on a good calcium enriched diet, importance of bone mineral density, early diagnosis and treatment of osteopenic patients can help in minimizing this problem.

LIMITATIONS OF STUDY:

One of the limitations of this study was the small sample size of patients and small ratio of edentulous women patient than male patients who were attending the dental college between given 2 months span for research.

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